

Data access and consent to use health systems data in clinical trials

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Executive Summary

Lay Summary: Making Health Research Easier and Safer

This Green Paper outlines how health systems data (HSD) - information related to a person's health, care, and medical history - can be used to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of clinical trials. Clinical trials are essential studies that test new treatments, and using HSD can help researchers identify, recruit, and follow up with participants more effectively. This approach has the potential to lead to better treatments and improved health outcomes. However, most clinical trials do not currently use HSD, largely due to difficulties in accessing the data. These challenges arise because the process for getting access to data is complicated and not the same across the UK. Different organisations follow different rules, and some organisations do not have enough staff or time to manage all the requests.

As a Working Group of the Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum, part of the HDR UK Transforming Data for Trials programme, we have examined these issues and proposed specific recommendations to streamline data access while ensuring the safe and ethical use of patient information. Key proposals include the establishment of a central national data service to oversee and coordinate data access approvals, and the development of a standardised framework for assessing participant consent to use and access their HSD. These measures aim to reduce delays, improve consistency, and support researchers in navigating legal and regulatory requirements.

Several problems were identified: the current system involves too many steps and differing rules, leading to confusion and inefficiency; there is variation in how consent is interpreted, which can delay approvals; data access teams are often under-resourced; new legal standards are sometimes unfairly applied to older studies; and trial participants are frequently excluded from decisions about how their data is used. These issues not only hinder research progress but also risk undermining public trust.

To address these challenges, the working group recommends (1) creating a centralised approval system; (2) establishing clear and objective standards for consent; and (3) introducing pre-approved pathways for commonly used datasets. These changes would simplify the process for researchers and reduce administrative burden. Importantly, the Green Paper emphasises the need for meaningful public engagement, including the involvement of citizen panels and shared patient and public forums, to ensure that the voices of trial participants and the wider public are heard and respected.

In summary, improving access to health systems data in clinical trials requires coordinated reform, clear guidance, and active public involvement. By making the process more transparent, consistent, and inclusive, we can accelerate health research while safeguarding individual rights and building public confidence in the use of health data.

Scientific Summary

Efficient and timely access to HSD is a major barrier to their wider use in clinical trials. Access is complex and fragmented for a number of reasons. In the UK, health data is a special category of personal data, and statutory and common law frameworks govern its use. There are different national jurisdictions along with a multiplicity of data assets and data custodians, with different (and sometimes changing) requirements for data access. In December 2024, we formed a Working Group from the Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum, part of the HDR UK Transforming Data for Trials programme, to address data access issues raised during our Forum meetings. The aims were: 1) to describe specific data access issues that affect clinical trials in the UK, e.g. assessment of trial consent procedures, and 2) to make recommendations to improve standardisation of consent assessment and streamline data access approval processes for clinical trials and consented cohorts.

The Forum comprises stakeholders from public and patient organisations, data custodians, clinical trialists and researchers, regulators, funders, and enabling networks such as UKCRC Registered Clinical Trials Units Network. We collated views and experiences of stakeholders on the topic of UK data access that were shared during breakout discussions of the two Forum meetings in April 2024 and September 2024, and we identified common themes. We then formed recommendations through Forum and Working Group discussions to address pertinent issues.

The five common issues identified were: 1) Fragmentation and complexity across the current data access approval systems; 2) variation in requirements for participant consent for data access; 3) limited capacity of data custodians to process data access applications; 4) retroactive application of new standards and legal frameworks; and 5) a lack of trial participant voices.

We discussed three approaches that could address most of these issues and incorporate patient and public voices throughout. Our recommendations to streamline data access in the UK are: 1) standardise procedures to assess the adequacy of trial participant consent to link and use HSD; 2) create a centralised data access approval system as recommended by the Sudlow Review (the newly formed Health Data

Research Service); and 3) develop a precedent set review pathway for common datasets and specific trial uses. We present these approaches and suggested implementation.

We welcome and encourage comments and contributions to help further this work. We are also interested to hear suggestions as to how best to implement the recommendations presented here and what barriers need to be addressed.

A [survey](#) has been created alongside this paper to establish level of agreement with the recommendations and capture feedback on implementation challenges.

This survey will remain open until 19 December 2025 (inclusive).

Overview

Purpose

To describe specific issues around data access that affect clinical trials in the UK, in particular the assessment of the trial consent procedures, and to constructively suggest ways to improve standardisation of consent assessment and streamline data access approval processes for the wider UK trials community. This paper proposes changes to solve some of the issues raised. It does not provide a framework for data access or detailed plans or processes but seeks to share collective experiences and recommendations for improvement.

Introduction/background

The recently published [Sudlow Review](#) clearly describes the potential benefits and opportunities of using health data safely and securely to improve health and wellbeing, and save lives.[1] It highlights the advances made by the RECOVERY trial to quickly answer key questions about treating severe COVID-19 through the judicious use of health data to obtain trial outcomes.[1, 2] Clinical trials are the most reliable method to assess new pharmacological, behavioural, and policy interventions, but they are resource-intensive, and can take a long time to complete. Health data has the potential to increase the efficiency of clinical trials by assisting identification, recruitment and follow-up of participants, leading to better treatments and health improvement.[3]

The main barrier to using health systems data in research, particularly in clinical trials, is efficient and timely data access,[1, 3-7] and the legal and administrative requirements to allow sharing of personal data,

including the assessment of whether the trial consent procedures are acceptable in relation to the release of health data. Clinical trials have been strictly regulated for decades, to protect participants and to ensure scientific rigour and integrity, and trial teams regularly securely manage personal data about trial participants in accordance with regulatory requirements.[8]

In most trials, participants have provided written informed consent to allow the use of their routinely collected health data and in most cases giving explicit consent for release of health data about them to the trial team, so there are expectations that such data are accessed and utilised for the trial. However, despite the advances made during the COVID-19 pandemic in the use of linked health data, delays in data access still severely impact timely delivery of clinical trials and their potential benefits.[1]

The UK health data landscape is complex for a number of reasons. Health data is a special category of personal data, and there are statutory and common law frameworks to govern such data; the UK General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; implemented within the Data Protection Act 2018 [DPA]) and the common law duty of confidentiality.[9-10] There are different common law mechanisms within UK national jurisdictions which further complicates data access. Other factors include multiplicity of data assets, fragmentation across regions, nations and healthcare settings, and the risk-averse approach of some data custodians, along with differing and changing requirements which may not be transparent. The complexity of how health data is accessed and used in clinical trials is shown in Figure 1 as an example. The Sudlow Review describes these issues, highlights specific examples and makes recommendations to facilitate safe and better use of health data.[1]

Learnings from the Forum and wider community

During the April 2024 meeting of the Forum, the following three priority areas were identified:

- Standardising the procedures used to assess consent to link and use health data and streamlining the approval process while ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements.
- Improving the incorporation of patients and the public voices in streamlined decision making.
- Building capacity and expertise within trials teams.

The first area was discussed more fully in the September 2024 meeting to explore issues that trialists face and make recommendations that could support the streamlining of processes. These are summarised below.

Figure 1: An example of data flows in a clinical trial using trial-specific and health systems data. Under UK GDPR, identifiable personal information is flowed from the Healthcare provider (research sites) to the Sponsor (into a restricted part of its secure data environment), which is shared with the Data Custodian organisation for data linkage. Linked pseudonymised data are securely transferred to the Sponsor to analyse with trial data within the Sponsor's secure data environment.

CRFs: Case report forms; UK GDPR: UK General Data Protection Regulation implemented within the Data Protection Act 2018; GP: General Practice; NHS: National Health Service. *Section 251 support is where section 251 of the NHS Act 2006 (England & Wales) is applied to allow disclosure of data without breaching the common law duty of confidentiality. Equivalent legislation in Northern Ireland to section 251 is the Health and Social Care (Control of Data Processing) Act 2016. The Scottish equivalent is overseen by the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care.

Issue 1: Fragmentation and Complexity

A key challenge is the fragmentation and complexity of the current data access approval systems for clinical trials. [3-6] This is a concern particularly for large UK-wide trials that require health data from multiple custodians and healthcare settings for recruitment or to obtain key outcomes. Delays occur due to the need for approvals from different data access committees, which creates huge administrative burden and slows the progress of important research.[4-6] Data sharing agreements have taken as long as 24 months to

obtain, and often with a further delay for data receipt; this is unacceptable for timely analyses and reporting of trial results.[4-6] Similar inefficiencies existed in the past when individual local ethics committees provided separate ethical opinions for trials. Reformation of the ethics review process since 1997 to a centralised system has significantly improved efficiency, and a similar approach could be beneficial for data access approvals.

Issue 2: Variation in requirements for consent to use health data

There is variation in requirements between data custodians and their data access committees, particularly in the assessment of the adequacy of consent for linkage with health systems data.[3-6] Under UK GDPR (article 12; DPA 2018 section 44), information provided to trial participants must describe the legal basis and purpose of data processing to meet their reasonable expectations of how their data will be used and managed.[9, 10] However, differing interpretations of trial information and consent materials by data custodians can lead to delays in approving projects, while also undermining the trust that participants place in both trial researchers and institutions. It also undermines the research ethics committee who review and approve these materials for ethical use by the trial team. Risk aversion can result in “default no” decisions on whether consent procedures are adequate to meet the common law and other legal requirements. This adds further administrative burden to trial teams who then need to seek permission to access data without participant consent from bodies such as the Confidentiality Advisory Group of the Health Research Authority in England and Wales and Public Benefit and Privacy Panels in Scotland and Northern Ireland.[4-5]

Issue 3: Limited capacity of data custodians to process data access applications

Some data custodians have very limited capacity to process data access requests.[5] Under-resourcing of data access teams and high staff turnover lead to significant delays in obtaining approvals.

Issue 4: Retroactive application of new standards and legal frameworks

Changes to existing standards for data access or legal frameworks (such as UK GDPR in 2018) has led to retroactive review of existing applications and sometimes previously approved access requests.[5] This is a particular issue for trials with longer term follow-up where consent was taken many years previously. Applying new frameworks to past decisions can erode the trust that participants have placed in trials, particularly if prior research is retroactively deemed non-compliant with new standards. This could severely damage relationships between trial researchers, data custodians, and trial participants, as it could call into question the validity of previously conducted research.

Issue 5: Lack of trial participant voices

The lack of trial participant involvement in data approval processes is seen as a missed opportunity. While participants are directly affected by how their data is used and have exposed themselves to the potential risks in a trial, they are often excluded from high-level decisions. This exclusion can lead to decisions that do not adequately reflect the concerns or priorities of trial participants, further eroding trust in the system.

Recommendations from the Forum

Several solutions were proposed to streamline the data access approval process, including standardisation of the assessment of trial consent to access health data.

Recommendation 1: A centralised data access approval system

The creation of a central body to oversee health data access approvals for clinical trials would address widespread delays and inconsistencies across the current system. Trialists often face complex, fragmented approval processes involving multiple custodians and different requirements. These inefficiencies slow the delivery of research and create unnecessary administrative burden, especially for UK cross-border trials.[1] Fragmented data access can also introduce bias from missing outcome data, which can lead to under- or over-estimation of treatment effects.

The recent announcement of the National Health Data Research Service (HDRS) offers a well-timed opportunity to embed our recommendation within its future development.[11] The HDRS has strong potential to enhance timely data access for trials, which supports research delivery and efficiency, and promotes trial participation to a broader range of participants. While legal variation across the UK makes full centralisation challenging and complex, coordination between nations should be prioritised to support consistency where possible. The remit of this new service and its relationship to existing structures, such as the Health Research Authority, must be clearly defined.

A single body could act as a point of contact for researchers, supporting navigation of legal and regulatory steps across organisations such as the Health Research Authority, Research Ethics Committees, and the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency. It should assess requests in line with public benefit, provide guidance on the suitability of research organisations, and coordinate a standardised application process.[11] A nationally recognised application form, similar to the IRAS system, would improve

consistency and reduce duplication. The recently developed SafeGUARDS principles should be adopted as the overarching governance framework for the service.[13, 14]

To support well-prepared requests, researchers should be able to access metadata, data dictionaries or synthetic datasets to better understand what data are available and define their needs before applying. Clarity on expected application timelines will temper expectations, and the service should aim towards progressing requests through to signed agreements and data access within an acceptable timeframe (e.g. within 6 months; further researcher engagement could determine what is widely acceptable). The service should also play a role in managing precedent set access pathways for frequently used datasets (see Recommendation 3). The creation of a standardised process flow along with several case study examples would guide researchers on the practical aspects of the new service.

To ensure trust and legitimacy, the body should be transparent and accountable,[12, 15-16] with visible public involvement such as citizen panels or independent advisory groups, in keeping with good practice standards (such as the Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative [PEDRI]).[17] Strong links with data custodians and alignment with existing models like the UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration and SAIL Databank would support successful implementation. Clear, regular communication with key stakeholders is vital during development and piloting of the service to ensure its fitness for purpose and stakeholder endorsement.

Once established, the service should monitor its impact on the research landscape over time, especially for clinical trials, by auditing data release registers, and performance indicators such as elapsed time from access application submission to data release. The service should also request feedback from applicants to allow for further streamlining of processes. Periodic review of the service, its strategy and related governance will maximise potential alignment opportunities between the devolved nations' frameworks.

Recommendation 2: An overarching, objective standard to assess the adequacy of consent to the release of health data

A standardised approach is needed to assess whether informed consent procedures in clinical trials are adequate for accessing health data. Trial teams often find that different data custodians interpret consent and participant information materials in inconsistent ways, leading to delays and additional approvals. This variability undermines efficiency and creates uncertainty for researchers.[1]

A national framework should provide clear guidance on what constitutes adequate consent and support consistency across data access committees. It should allow for variation in study design, patient populations, and legal requirements across jurisdictions, but set out core expectations for clarity, scope and participant understanding. It must be adaptable and forward-looking, recognising that consent should be valid not only at the time it is given but also under evolving data governance frameworks. To ensure alignment across the UK, the framework should be developed with NHS research governance and ethics authorities across the UK nations (Health Research Authority, NHS Research Scotland, Health and Care Research Wales, Health and Social Care Northern Ireland), the National Institute for Health and Care Research, and the UK Clinical Research Collaboration (UKCRC) as a minimum.

Specific issues raised by the Forum include the treatment of historical consent that predates modern data linkage practices, and the lack of shared standards around renewing or modifying consent over time. It is noted that the public is often unsure whether their NHS data is used in research, or how to check or update their choices. Clearer guidance will benefit both researcher and public understanding on the use of their health data in clinical trials.

The framework should help researchers avoid language that is either too broad or too restrictive. Standardised wording should be developed to enhance both transparency and the ability to use health data for future ethically approved research projects. This includes ensuring that consent allows for appropriate data sharing and linkage, while still respecting participant autonomy and privacy. This would reduce duplication and avoid decisions being made on the basis of subjective interpretation. The framework should also allow for the use of different mechanisms (e.g. written, electronic) and forms of consent such as layered information and multi-step consent. Exemplars will support trust and understanding of the framework by researchers and the public and healthcare professionals.

Ongoing public engagement must be built into the development and review of the framework.[17] Visible involvement from patients, trial participants and citizen panels is essential to maintaining trust.[18] It is recognised that there may be difficulty in achieving consensus during the development of the framework, so this must be carefully communicated to patients and the public.

Better communication is needed about what people can expect in terms of data sharing, and how their consent will be used. Educational initiatives, including integration into the national curriculum, could also improve wider understanding of data access and governance.

Recommendation 3: A precedent set review pathway for common datasets and specific trial uses

Creating precedent set review pathways for datasets that are frequently requested for specific trial purposes would improve consistency, reduce delays, and ease the administrative burden on both researchers and data custodians. These pathways would outline standard requirements and timelines for access requests where the data use is well established (e.g. utility evidenced from publications) and regularly approved.

For example, the most accessed datasets for informing clinical trial outcomes are held by NHS England (previously NHS Digital) and Public Health Scotland (was ISD Scotland), in particular the Civil Registration of Deaths and the National Records of Scotland Deaths data for mortality outcomes.[19-23] Hence, a precedent set review pathway to gaining access to data for survival related and specific time-to-event outcomes could significantly reduce administrative burden on data custodians and clinical trial staff. Additional potential datasets include those used to support outcome measurements in diabetes, cardiovascular disease, asthma, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, especially where there is evidence of data utility in terms of clinical relevance, accuracy, and completeness. Reviews of trial publications and data access registers describe the types of health data that are most requested for clinical trials use as well as the reasons, e.g. for participant recruitment, primary outcome ascertainment.

To remain useful, precedent set pathways must be regularly reviewed and updated by data custodians and those responsible for approving data access (e.g. HDRS). This should be done in collaboration with researchers, data custodians, patients and members of the public to ensure the pathways continue to reflect research priorities and clinical needs. Importantly, these pathways must not become mandatory or exclusive. Researchers must still be able to request other datasets or make non-standard requests and access decisions should continue to reflect the full range of research questions being asked.

Good governance will be critical. Relying too heavily on predefined pathways could lead to narrow or biased patterns of data use. To guard against this, data use registers should be monitored to support transparency and ensure a balanced spread of approvals. Clinical trial publications can also be systematically reviewed as described in Appendix 1. These safeguards will help prevent the system from unintentionally discouraging innovative or less common studies or encouraging the use of objective measures without patient-reported outcomes or experience measures (e.g. biomarkers).

Precedent set pathways should not affect legal or consent requirements. All requests must continue to meet existing governance standards, regardless of whether they follow a standard route. Clear public communication will be important to explain how these pathways work and what protections remain in

place.[17] This will help to maintain trust and support public understanding of how data is used in clinical trials.

Enabling effective implementation

The Working Group identified several system-wide actions needed to support implementation of all three recommendations. These cross-cutting themes highlight the broader context and infrastructure required for success:

- Involve experienced clinical trialists from the Transforming Data for Trials (TDfT) programme and its Community Insight Group of representatives from clinical trials units across the UK.
- Engage the public meaningfully through mechanisms such as citizen panels and shared PPIE forums, in keeping with good practice standards of PEDRI and HRA principles.[17, 18]
- Coordinate public engagement efforts to avoid duplication, align messaging, and ensure a diversity of voices is heard.[17]
- Recognise that the pace and scale of change within the NHS may lead to confusion or mistrust, and ensuring clear, consistent communication to build and maintain public confidence.
- Frame system reform as an opportunity to strengthen patient-centred data governance and highlight the benefits of new models.
- Develop clear organisational maps to show how new and existing bodies (i.e. the proposed central service, citizen panels, custodians) will relate to one another.
- Use practical examples (use cases) and visual tools to make the recommendations more accessible, actionable and relevant to a broad audience.

Conclusion

There is an urgent need to standardise assessment of consent procedures and streamline data access approvals for health research, particularly clinical trials.[1] Establishing a national body for data access with a citizen panel, creating an objective consent framework, and building capacity within approval committees are all critical steps forward. Involving trial participants more directly and balancing the risks of data misuse with the potential benefits of data use would ensure that the clinical trial process is both ethical and efficient. These solutions would not only enhance the efficiency of clinical trials but also build the public trust necessary for future advancements in health research.

Next steps

We welcome and encourage comments and contributions to help further this work. We are also interested to hear suggestions as to how best to implement the recommendations presented here and what barriers to implementation need to be addressed.

A [survey](#) has been created alongside this paper to establish level of agreement with the recommendations and capture feedback on the recommendations and implementation challenges.

This survey will remain open until 19 December 2025 (inclusive). All feedback and contributions will be incorporated into an updated White Paper that will be shared with the UK Health Data Research Alliance Council in early 2026, with a view to publishing as soon as possible thereafter.

Working group members and contributors

Macey Murray, University College London (UCL)

Marion Mafham, University of Oxford.

Fiona Lugg-Widger, Cardiff University.

Stephen Burrows, UK Health Data Research Alliance.

Marina Bobou, UCL.

Caroline Brocklehurst, TDfT Public Advisory Group.

Rachel Brophy, HDR UK, Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group.

Sarah Chave, TDfT Public Advisory Group.

Michael Cook, Our Future Health.

Michelle Goonasekera, University of Oxford.

Kerry Hood, UKCRC Registered Clinical Trials Units Network.

Simon Jobson, UK Health Data Research Alliance.

Emma Lagerstedt, Understanding Patient Data.

Isla Mackenzie, University of Dundee.

Paul Mouncey, ICNARC.

Grisma Patel, UCL.

Kate Roberts, UCL.

Matt Sydes, UCL (honorary professor), HDR UK Fellow.

Sharon Tonner, University of Oxford.

Rob Trubey, Cardiff University.

Tim Williams, Clinical Practice Research Datalink.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Monitoring precedent set pathways

A proposed approach to monitor and adapt precedent set pathways is by periodic review publications of data utility comparison studies (DUCKs) and data-enabled trials (Sydes et al., 2024). DUCKs are used to assess whether health systems data can replace trial-specific data collection methods in clinical trials. For example, DUCKs may provide evidence that a specific health dataset is accurate and contemporaneous for a particular trial outcome or event. If there is sufficient evidence to provide confidence in using this health dataset, then clinical trialists may design their trials to use it. Data access could be streamlined by including the dataset and its particular trial use within the precedent set pathway. Periodic review of data-enabled trial publications in bibliographic database and in grey literature (e.g. ClinicalTrials.gov and EU Clinical Trials Register) will also identify frequently used health system datasets and their trial uses.[21, 22] Search terms will include “routine data”, “rand*”, “trial”, “RCT”, “randomised controlled trial”, etc.